

Notes

Rhenium XII*. A Polarographic Study of the Complex Dioxobis (ethylenediamine) rhenium(V) Chloride

M. C. CHAKRAVORTI** and C. K. DAS***

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology,
Kharagpur - 721 302.

Manuscript received 4 August 1977, revised 11 November 1977,
accepted 1 February 1978

RHENIUM exhibits a widely different oxidation states and offers an interesting field for investigation by polarographic method. Various workers¹⁻⁶ have studied the polarographic reduction of perrhenate in a variety of supporting electrolytes, but studies with rhenium complexes as the starting material are very rare⁷⁻¹⁰. One of us has previously investigated¹⁰ the polarographic reduction of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ and found that under the experimental conditions the complex is reversibly reduced to a Re(IV) complex containing two pyridine molecules.

The only well known ethylenediamine complex of rhenium is $[\text{ReO}_2\text{en}_2]\text{Cl}$ and is formed by the oxidation of $\text{K}_2[\text{ReCl}_6]$ by air in the presence of ethylenediamine¹¹. In the lower valency states the ethylenediamine complexes of rhenium are rare and as such it is interesting to study the polarographic reduction of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{en}_2]\text{Cl}$.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of BDH Analar grade or E. Merck's GR quality. Potassium perrhenate used was of Degussa (West Germany). $\text{K}_2[\text{ReCl}_6]$ and $[\text{ReO}_2\text{en}_2]\text{Cl}$ were prepared according to known procedures^{11,12}. Distilled water redistilled in an all glass apparatus with a little KMnO_4 and KOH , was used for preparing all the solutions.

Polarograms were recorded in a Czechoslovak pen-recording polarograph (Polarograph, type LP 7 in working conjunction with EZ 7 Electronic compensation Line Recorder, Laboratory Instruments, National Corporation, Praha) with a dropping mercury electrode and an external saturated calomel electrode. At a mercury height of 30 cm the capillary of the dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics: $m=1.79$ mg/sec and $t=5.21$ sec/drop (in open circuit and in 0.2M KCL solution containing 0.005% gelatin).

The pH of the solutions was measured by a Digital pH Meter (pH 822, Electronic Corporation of India Limited).

The solutions for polarography were made by mixing stock solutions of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{en}_2]\text{Cl}$, potassium chloride

and gelatin and diluting to a known volume. The strengths of potassium chloride and gelatin were kept constant throughout (0.2M and 0.005% respectively). Pure hydrogen was passed through the solutions to remove dissolved oxygen. For recording the polarograms in the presence of ethylenediamine pure hydrogen was first passed through a bubbler containing the same electrolyte of identical concentration and then through the test solution.

Results and Discussion

The polarogram of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{en}_2]\text{Cl}$ in 0.2 M potassium chloride gave a well defined cathodic reduction wave with a half-wave potential of -1.150 V vs SCE at 28°.

The plots of i_d vs $(h_{eff})^{1/2}$ and i_d vs C (where $h_{eff} = h - 3.1/m^{1/3} t^{1/3}$ and C = concentration of the complex) were found to be linear indicating that the reduction was diffusion-controlled. The plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log(i_d - i)$ was found to be linear with a slope of 0.063, which is almost equal to the expected value of 0.060 for $n=1$. Thus, under the experimental conditions Re(V) in $[\text{ReO}_2\text{en}_2]\text{Cl}$ is reversibly reduced to Re(IV).

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF HALF-WAVE POTENTIAL WITH INCREASING CONCENTRATION OF ETHYLENEDIAMINE

Concentration of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{en}_2]\text{Cl}$, $0.98 \times 10^{-3} M$ Temperature 28°		
Concentration of ethylenediamine $M \times 10^3$	$E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE	pH of the solution
—	-1.150	5.95
4.5	-1.162	10.14
7.1	-1.172	10.52
12.2	-1.183	
17.3	-1.190	
22.4	-1.195	10.85
27.5	-1.200	
53.0	-1.210	11.06

The $E_{1/2}$ values were found to shift towards more negative direction with increasing ethylenediamine concentration (Table 1). For determining the composition of the complex in the reduced state, the half-wave potentials of the electrolytes were measured as a function of the concentration of ethylenediamine which was progressively increased. The half-wave potentials when plotted against the logarithm of the

* Part XI. M. C. CHAKRAVORTI and C. K. DAS, *Inorg. Chim. Acta.*, 1976, 19, 249.

** To whom correspondence may be addressed.

*** Department of Chemistry, Jalpaiguri Govt. Engineering College, Jalpaiguri.

concentration of the corresponding ethylenediamine gave a straight line with a slope of 0.049. From the following equation¹³

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = E^{\circ} + \frac{0.060}{n} \log \frac{K_{ox}}{K_{red}} - \frac{0.060}{n} (p-q) \log C$$

the slope of the curve is $\frac{0.060}{n} (p-q)$. Putting the value of n as one and p , the number of molecules of ethylenediamine in dioxobis(ethylenediamine)rhenium(V) chloride, as two, the value of q (the number of molecules of ethylenediamine in the new complex) comes to 1.19, which when rounded up becomes equal to one. The most probable composition of the Re(IV) complex appears to be $ReenCl_4$. Though this particular compound has not been reported, a similar compound $ReenI_4$ has been isolated by us¹⁴. A large number of analogous compounds with other ligands are well known¹⁵, viz. $ReCl_4L_2$ (where $L = py, \frac{1}{2}$ bipy, trialkyl phosphine, etc.).

In passing from the minimum ($4.5 \times 10^{-3} M$) to the maximum ($5.3 \times 10^{-2} M$) concentration of ethylenediamine added, the pH of the medium increased by about one unit (Table 1). Polarograms of $[ReO_2en_2]Cl$ were

Fig. 1. Polarogram of $[ReO_2en_2]Cl$ ($5.05 \times 10^{-4} M$) in 0.2M KCl.

Fig. 2. Plot of E_{de} vs $\log (i_d - i) / i$

Fig. 3. Plot of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs logarithm of concentration of ethylenediamine.

recorded at different pH values (upto a pH of 11) by adding different volumes of caustic soda solution and it was observed that there was no change in $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$. It can thus be assumed that the change in $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ with the increasing concentration of ethylenediamine was solely due to the variation in the concentration of ligand ethylenediamine.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation (West Germany) for a gift potassium perrhenate and Miss B. Dutta for recording the polarograms. Thanks are also due to the Government of West Bengal for sponsoring one of us (C.K.D.) under the Q.I.P. Scheme,

References

1. J. HEYROVSKY, *Nature*, 1935, 135, 870.
2. J. J. LINGANE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1001.
3. C. L. RULFS and P. J. ELVING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 3284.
4. R. COLTON, J. DALZIEL, W. P. GRIFFITH and G. WILKINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 71.
5. D. BANERJEA and K. K. TRIPATHI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1961, 21, 307.
6. A. NARAYANAN and F. UMLAND, *Analytica. Chim. Acta.*, 1971, 54, 368.
7. B. JEZOWSKA-TRZEBIATOWSKA and J. DANOWSKA, *Z. Physik. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1959, 212, 29.
8. B. K. SEN, N. N. GHOSH and P. B. SARKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 708.
9. E. I. STIEFEL, R. EISENBERG, R. C. ROSENBERG and H. B. GRAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 88, 2956.
10. M. C. CHAKRAVORTI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 834.
11. R. K. MURMANN, *Inorg. Synthesis*, 1966, 8, 173.
12. G. W. WATT and R. J. THOMPSON, *Inorg. Synthesis*, 1963, 7, 189.
13. I. M. KOLTHOFF and J. J. LINGANE, "Polarography", Interscience publishers, Inc., New York, N. Y., 1946, p. 172.
14. M. C. CHAKRAVORTI and C. K. DAS, Unpublished work.
15. J. E. FERGUSSON, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, 1, 459.